

Council for
BRITISH ARCHAEOLOGY
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20th November, 1972

Dear Andrew,

Thank you for your letter of 18th November providing the information I needed for the Qatar project. I will let you know how plans go and when the Qatar Government has formally accepted the proposals - if they do so. I will also, as I promised, find out whether you can use your current passport.

All good wishes,

Yours,

Andrew Williamson, Esq.,
West End,
Wootton,
Woodstock,
Oxon.